

YOSHLAR DUNYOQARASHI SHAKLLANISHIDA MILLIY TARBIYA VA TA'LIMNING AHAMIYATI

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Annotatsiya. Yoshlar tarbiyasi. Yoshlar ongiga milliy-ma'naviy qadriyatlarni singdirish.

Shaxs tarbiyasida axloqning roli. Milliy tarbiyani ta'lim bilan uyg'unlashtirish. Yoshlar tarbiyasida umumta'lim maktablarining roli. Ta'lim bosqichlari. Yoshlarga bo'sh vaqtlarini mazmunli o'tkazish maqsadida amalga oshirilayotgan ishlar keng imkoniyatlar. Milliy qadriyat va tarbiya.

Kalit so'zlar: Tarbiya. Milliy ong. Qadriyat. Axloq. Milliy g'oya. ma'naviyat. Kelajak. Milliy g'urur. Ma'naviy boyluk. Jamiyat taraqqiyoti.

THE IMPORTANCE OF NATIONAL UPBRINGING AND EDUCATION IN THE FORMATION OF YOUTH'S WORLDVIEW

Annotation: Youth education. Inculcating national and spiritual values in the minds of young people. The role of morality in the upbringing of a person. Combining national education with education. The role of secondary schools in educating young people. Stages of education.

There is a wide range of opportunities for young people to spend their free time meaningfully. National values and education.

Keywords: Education. National consciousness. Value. Morality. National ideology, spirituality. The future. National pride. Spiritual wealth. Community development.

ЗНАЧЕНИЕ НАЦИОНАЛЬНОГО ВОСПИТАНИЯ И ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ В ФОРМИРОВАНИИ МИРОВОЗЗРЕНИЯ МОЛОДЕЖИ

Аннотация. Образование молодежи. Привитие национальных и духовных ценностей в сознании молодежи. Роль нравственности в воспитании личности.

Гармонизация национального образования с образованием. Роль общеобразовательной школы в воспитании молодежи. Образовательные этапы. У молодых людей есть много возможностей провести свободное время с пользой.

Национальная ценность и образование.

Ключевые слова: Образование. Национальное сознание. Ценить. Этика. Национальная идея. духовность. Будущее. Национальная гордость. Духовное богатство. Развитие сообщества.

Yoshlar ongiga milliy-ma'naviy qadriyatlarimizni singdirish uchun biz juda katta boy merosga egamiz. Jumladan, zardushtiylik dinining muqaddas diniy asari hisoblanmish “Avesto” dan unumli foydalanish samarali hisoblanadi. Chunki, ajdodlarimizning eng mo'tabar qo'lyozma asarining mo'tabarligi, qimmatini shundan iboratki, bu asar diniy, falsafiy, siyosiy, ijtimoiy – tarixiy ma'lumotga ega bo'lish bilan bir qatorda ta'limiy – tarbiyaviy ahamiyatga egalidir. Shuning uchun ham bu asar bizning ma'naviy boyligimiz hisoblanadi.

Talaba – yoshlarimizni milliy-ma'naviy qadriyatlar bilan boyitishda “Avesto” bilan birga “Qur'oni Karim” va “Hadisi Sharif” kabi muqaddas manbalarning ahamiyati beqiyos.

Har bir shaxsning, jamiyatning ravnaq topishida ahloqning asosiy roli tasvirlanadi.

Zero, jamiyat a'zosi bo'lgan har bir kishining axloqsizligi jamiyatga qay darajada zarar etkazsa, yaxshi axloqli kishilar uning ravnaqiga shuncha hissa qo'shadilar.

Inson va jamiyatning mavjudligini ta'minlaydigan qadriyatlar milliy tarbiya tufayli, ajdodlardan asta-sekin tadrijiy ravishda avlodlarga o'tadi. Milliy tarbiya atamasi keng va tor ma'nolarda ishlatiladi. Keng ma'noda, u inson shaxsini shakllantirishga, uning ishlab chiqarish va ijtimoiy, madaniy, ma'rifiy hayotda faol ishtirokini ta'minlashga qaratilgan barcha ma'naviy ta'sirlar, tadbirlar, harakatlar, intilishlar yig'indisini anglatadi. Bunday tushunishda milliy tarbiya faqat oila, maktab, bolalar va yoshlar tashkilotlarida olib boriladigan tarbiyaviy ishlarni emas, balki butun ijtimoiy tuzum, uning etakchi g'oyalari, adabiyot, san'at, kino, radio, TV, OAV va boshqalarni ham o'z ichiga oladi. Shuningdek, keng ma'nodagi milliy tarbiya tarkibiga bu sohada ta'lim va ma'lumot olish ham kiradi. Tor ma'noda, milliy tarbiya muayyan shaxsning ma'naviy rivoji, dunyoqarashi, axloqiy qiyofasi, estetik didi o'stirilishiga yo'naltirilgan pedagogik faoliyatni anglatadi. Buni oila va tarbiyaviy muassasalar hamda jamoat tashkilotlari amalga oshiradilar.

Bizga ma'lumki, har qanday tarbiya ta'lim bilan chambarchas bog'liq holdagina mavjud bo'ladi. Chunki, ta'lim va ma'lumot olish jarayonida shaxsning faqat bilimi ko'payibgina qolmay, balki ma'naviy-axloqiy sifatleri qaror topishi ham tezlashadi. Ana shu sababdan ham otabobolarimiz qadimdan bebaho boylik bo'lmish ilmu ma'rifat, ta'lim va tarbiyani inson kamoloti va millat ravnaqining eng asosiy sharti va garovi deb bilganlar. Prezident Sh.Mirziyoyev

ta'kidlagani kabi, "Ta'lim-tarbiya-ong mahsuli, lekin ayni vaqtda ong darajasi va uning rivojini ham belgilaydigan, ya'ni, xalq ma'naviyatini shakllantiradigan va boyitadigan eng muhim omildir.

Binobarin, ta'lim-tarbiya tizimini va shu asosda ongni o'zgartirmasdan turib, ma'naviyatni rivojlantirib bo'lmaydi. Shu bois bu sohada yuzaki, rasmiy yondashuvlarga, puxta o'ylanmagan ishlarga mutlaqo yo'l qo'yib bo'lmaydi. Maktab, ta'lim-tarbiya masalasi davlat va jamiyat nazoratida bo'lishi asosiy qonunimizda belgilab qo'yilgan. Shu bilan birga, bu keng jamoatchilik, butun xalqimizning ishtiroki va qo'llab-quvvatlashini talab qiladigan umummilliy masaladir... Bu haqda fikr yuritganda, men Abdulla Avloniyning "Tarbiya biz uchun yo hayot-yo mamot, yo najot-yo halokat, yo saodat-yo falokat masalasidir" degan chuqur ma'noli so'zlarini eslayman. Buyuk ma'rifatparvar bobomizning bu so'zlari asrimiz boshida millatimiz uchun qanchalar muhim va dolzarb bo'lgan bo'lsa, hozirgi vaqtda ham biz uchun shunchalik, balki undan ham ko'ra muhim va dolzarb ahamiyat kasb etadi".

Istiqlol yillarida mamlakatimizda milliy tarbiyani amalga oshiradigan o'quv muassasalari va umumta'lim maktablarining moddiy-texnik bazasini mustahkamlashga e'tiborni kuchaytirish eng muhim va jiddiy masalaga aylandi. Shu maqsadda yurtimizda Kadrlar tayyorlash milliy dasturi amalga oshirilmogda, uning uzviy va mantiqiy davomi bo'lmish Maktab ta'limini rivojlantirish umummilliy davlat dasturi qabul qilindi.

Unga muvofiq, yurtimizda mavjud bo'lgan o'n mingga yaqin umumta'lim maktabining moddiy-texnik bazasini mustahkamlash, ta'lim jarayonining mazmunini tubdan takomillashtirish, o'qituvchilarning mehnatini moddiy va ma'naviy rag'batlantirish bo'yicha katta ishlar qilinmogda.

Muxtasar qilib aytganda, oxirgi yillarda ta'lim-tarbiya sohasida amalga oshirgan, ko'lami va mohiyatiga ko'ra ulkan ishlarimiz biz ko'zlagan ezgu niyatlarimizga erishish, hech kimdan kam bo'lmaydigan hayot barpo etish, yoshlarimiz, butun xalqimizning ma'naviy yuksalishi yo'lida mustahkam zamin yaratdi, desak, hech qanday xato bo'lmaydi. Yuqoridagi fikrlardan ko'rinib turibdiki, milliy tarbiya har qanday jamiyat va mamlakat hayotida hal qiluvchi ahamiyat kasb etadi. Chunki, uning o'sishi va taraqqiyoti uchun moddiy va ma'naviy boyliklar ishlab chiqarish to'xtovsiz ravishda yuksalib borishi lozim. Buning uchun yosh avlod ushbu boyliklarni yaratishda o'z ajdodlaridan yuqoriroq darajaga ko'tarilmog'i darkor.

Yoshlarni ham jismoniy, ham ma'naviy jihatdan to'g'ri tarbiyalashda zamonaviy meditsina, pedagogika, psixologiya fanlari tavsiyalarini har qaysi oilada joriy qilish ayniqsa zarur. Har bir oila, ota-ona, eng avvalo, bola timsolida shaxsni ko'rishi, uning uchun shaxsga tegishli

barcha huquq va erkinliklar ta'minlashi borasida o'zining mas'ul ekanligini doimo his etib turishi nihoyatda muhim.

Milliy tarbiyada milliy g'oyaga, milliy g'ururni yuksaltirishga xizmat qiladigan timsollar, ramzlarning har biri – katta bir darslik, kuchli tarbiya vositasi hisoblanadi. Bundan tashqari, buyuk ajdodlar tavallud sanalarini nishonlash ham ma'naviy va tarixiy ahamiyatga ega. Bunday marosimlarni o'tkazish orqali yoshlar yangi qadriyatlar asosida tarbiyalanadilar, ular qalbiga tarixni anglash va qadrlash, o'tmishga hurmat bilan yondashish, ularni asrab-avaylash, shu xalqqa mansubligi bilan g'ururlanish tuyg'ulari singdiriladi.

Birinchi prezidentimiz I.A.Karimov istiqlolning ilk kunlaridanoq boshlab, avvalombor barchamizni o'sib kelayotgan yosh avlodning ma'naviy tarbiyasiga katta javobgarlik hissi bilan yondashishga da'vat etib, buning sababini “Yoshlar xalq ma'naviyatining munosib egalaridir” deb uqtirganlar. Yoshlarimizga murojaat etib: “Shu aziz va muqaddas Vatanimiz sizlarga, sizlarning har biringizga ishonadi. Ana shunday yuksak ishonch barchangizga madadkor bo'lsin, kuch-quvvat bersin. Shu ishonchga hamisha munosib bo'ling, aziz farzandlarim” deya samimiy tuyg'ularini izhor etganlari ham bu biz yoshlarga Buyuk yurtning baxtli yoshlariga berilayotgan katta ishonchdir.

Mamlakatning buyuk kelajagi ma'naviy barkamol insonlarga tayangan holda yaratiladi.

Boshqacha aytganda, ma'naviy barkamol insonlarga buyuk kelajakni yaratadilar.

Shu bois, ma'naviy barkamol insonni, sog'lom avlodni tarbiyalash yurtimiz uchun muhim va dolzarb masala bo'lib qolmoqda. Demak, “Farzandlarimizni mustaqil va keng fikrlash qobiliyatiga ega bo'lgan, ongli yashaydigan komil insonlar etib voyaga yetkazish – ta'lim-tarbiya sohasining asosiy maqsadi va vazifasi bo'lishi lozim” degan azmushijoat ustuvor bo'lgan mamlakat yuksak marralarga erishadi. Chunki har bir mamlakatda barqaror taraqqiyot va modernizatsiyani amalga oshiruvchilar-ajdodlariga qaraganda kuchli, bilimli va dono yangi avlodlardir. Buning yorqin misoli komil inson g'oyasi yoshlarimizning intellektual salohiyatini vatan ravnaqi, xalq farovonligiga yo'naltiruvchi g'oyaviy poydevor vazifasini bajarmoqda.

Yoshlar O'zbekiston uchun, uning buyuk kelajagi uchun sport, intellektual, texnologik, ijod maydonlariga kirib, g'olib bo'lmoqdalar. Buning yorqin misoli 2 milliondan ortiq yoshlarimiz sportning 30 dan ziyod turi bilan muntazam shug'ullanib, jahon arenalarida yuksak marralarga erishmoqdalar. Bugun hech kimga sir emaski, biz yashayotgan XXI asr – intellectual boylik hukm qiladigan asr. Intellektual boylikka yuksak bilimli yoshlarimiz orqali erishishimiz mumkin.

Bilimli va intellektual rivojlangan avlodni tarbiyalash vazifasini doimo o'zining asosiy ustuvor yo'nalishlar qatoriga qo'yadigan davlatgina o'zini namoyon eta olishi mumkin. Yoshlari yuksak ma'naviyatli, bilimli va intellectual yetuk bo'lsa, u davlatning xalqi, fuqarolari baxtiyor bo'ladi. Ta'lim – imkoniyatlar tengligini ta'minlaydigan buyuk mezon bo'lib, u jamiyat aql – zakovatining yuksalishi, raqobatdoshlikning kuchayishi va yutuqlar ko'payishining muhim omili vazifasini o'taydi.

Umuman olganda, yoshlarning etnik qiyofasi millatning bugungi milliy tarbiyasi, mentaliteti, madaniyatining o'zaro dialektik munosabati vositasida shakllanadi. Ma'naviy jihatdan yaxshi tarbiya olgan shaxs o'z aqli, o'z tafakkuri, o'z mehnati, o'z mas'uliyati bilan ongli ravishda, ozod va hur fikrli inson bo'lib yashaydi.

REFERENCES

1. Obid o'g'li, B. O., & Zaynievich, O. M. (2024). BUXORO VA JUNG'OR XONLIKLARI O'RTASIDA SIYOSIY MUNOSABATLAR TARIXI.
2. Boltayev, O. (2024). QO'QON XONLIGINING XVIII ASR SO'NGI CHORAGIDA BUXORO, XIVA VA KO'CHMANCHILAR BILAN OLIB BORGAN DIPLOMATIYASI. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(10), 64-68.
3. Obid o'g'li, B. O. QO'QON XONLIGINING XVIII ASR SO'NGI CHORAGIDA BUXORO, XIVA VA KO'CHMANCHILAR BILAN OLIB BORGAN DIPLOMATIYASI.
4. Boltaev, O. (2024). BUKHARA'S CARAVAN TRADE AND ITS ROLE ON THE SILK ROAD. *Analytical Journal of Education and Development*, 4(10), 293-297.
5. Boltayev, O. (2024). XX ASR BOSHLARIDA GERMANIYA VA TURKIYA ITTIFOQINING MARKAZIY OSIYOGA TA'SIRI. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(12), 556-564.
6. Boltayev, O. (2023). A GENERAL DESCRIPTION OF THE POLITICAL AND DIPLOMATIC PROCESSES IN CENTRAL ASIA IN THE MIDDLE OF THE 18TH CENTURY. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(9), 145-149.
7. Muyiddinov, B. (2023). XII-XIII ASRLAR DAVRIDA BUXORODA ILM – FANNING RIVOJLANISHI. *SCHOLAR*, 1(28), 341–345. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10027071>

8. Muyiddinov Bekali. (2023). MO'G'ULLAR BOSQINI DAVRIDA BUXORONING AYANCHLI TAQDIRI. TADQIQOTLAR.UZ, 25(2), 212–215. Retrieved from <http://tadqiqotlar.uz/index.php/new/article/view/308>
9. Muyiddinov Bekali. (2023). THE ROLE OF BUKHARA AND OTHER CITIES IN THE MILITARY ART AND ARMY STRUCTURE OF KHOREZMSHAHS. ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ, 35(3), 55–58. Retrieved from <https://www.newjournal.org/index.php/01/article/view/10035>
10. Muyiddinov, B. (2024). BARTHOLD'S "СОЧИНЕНИЯ. ТОМ I. ТУРКЕСТАН В ЭПОХУ МОНГОЛЬСКОГО НАШЕСТВИЯ" THE HISTORY OF THE CREATION OF THE WORK. MODERN SCIENCE AND RESEARCH, 3(1), 699–702. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10552555>
11. Muyiddinov, B. (2024). THE ROLE OF MILITARY REFORMS IN THE BUKHARA KHANATE IN THE LIFE OF THE STATE UNDER THE SHAYBANIDS. MODERN SCIENCE AND RESEARCH, 3(2), 646–648. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10668887>
12. MB Bahodir o'g'li. (2024). Military Art of Turkish Khaganate in the Early Middle Ages. European Journal of Innovation in Nonformal Education, 4(16), 223–227. <https://inovatus.es/index.php/ejine/article/view/2705/2586>
13. ХОРАЗМШОИДЛАР ДАВЛАТИ НАЙОТИДА ТУРКОН ХОТУННИНГ О'РНИ. (2024). MEDICINE, PEDAGOGY AND TECHNOLOGY: THEORY AND PRACTICE, 2(4), 463–469. <https://universalpublishings.com/index.php/mpttp/article/view/5192>
14. Muyiddinov Bekali Bahodir o'g'li. (2024). The coronation and campaigns of Alexander The Great. МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА, 2(5), 400–412. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11222912>
15. Muyiddinov Bekali. (2024). COVERAGE OF LEGAL ISSUES IN "AVESTO". МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА, 2(6), 222–230. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12191420>
16. MUYIDDINOV BEKALI, & QORYOG'DIEV Z. (2022). ABOUT THE CONQUEST OF BUKHARA BY THE KHOREZMSHAHS. International Journal of Philosophical Studies and Social Sciences, 2(3), 158–161. Retrieved from <https://www.ijpsss.iscience.uz/index.php/ijpsss/article/view/383>
17. Muyiddinov Bekali Bahodir o'g'li. (2024). History of State Institutions in the Kushan State, Which Founded Statehood on the Territory of Central Asia. EUROPEAN

- JOURNAL OF INNOVATION IN NONFORMAL EDUCATION, 4(9), 184–188.
Retrieved from <https://inovatus.es/index.php/ejine/article/view/4070>
18. Bahodir o'g'li, M. B. (2024). Avesto is an Ancient Written Monument Containing Information About the Life of the Peoples of Central Asia. *Miasto Przyszłości*, 53, 970–975. Retrieved from <https://miastoprzyszlosci.com.pl/index.php/mp/article/view/4982>
 19. Muyiddinov Bekali. (2024). SOMONIYLAR DAVLATIDA HARBIYLARGA BERILGAN E'TIBOR VA HARBIY SAN'AT. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14209121>
 20. Muyiddinov Bekali. (2024). O'ZLIKNI NAMOYON QILISHDA XALQ DOSTONLARINING AMALIY AHAMIYATI VA KITOBIY DOSTONLARNING O'ZIGA XOSLIGI. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14528916>
 21. Ilniyazovich, S. F. (2023). RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALARNING TARIX FANINI O'QITISHDAGI AHAMIYATI.
 22. Ilniyoz o'g'li, S. F. (2023). ETNOGRAFIK TADQIQOTLARDA QORAQALPOQ XALQINING YORITILISHI.
 23. Sadullayev U. (2024). MAHALLA: UNDERSTANDING THE CONCEPT. *Medicine, Pedagogy and Technology: Theory and Practice*, 2(4), 376–385.
 24. Sadullaev U. (2024). USE OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY IN EDUCATION. *Medicine, Pedagogy and Technology: Theory and Practice*, 2(5), 344–352.
 25. Sadullaev, U. (2024). EDUCATION AND ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE: A NEW ERA OF OPPORTUNITY. *Medicine, Pedagogy and Technology: Theory and Practice*, 2(6), 238–241.
 26. Shokir o'g'li, S. U. (2024). Media literacy is a requirement of the modern world. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATION IN NONFORMAL EDUCATION*, 4(3), 276-280.
 27. Shokir o'g'li, S. U. (2024). Media literacy is a requirement of the modern world. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATION IN NONFORMAL EDUCATION*, 4(3), 276-280.
 28. Shokir o'g'li, S. U. (2024). The Development of Culture and Art during the Timurid Era: the Development of Architecture and its Characteristics. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATION IN NONFORMAL EDUCATION*, 4(9), 133-138.

29. Shokir o'g'li, S. U. (2024). The Development of Culture and Art during the Timurid Era: the Development of Architecture and its Characteristics. EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATION IN NONFORMAL EDUCATION, 4(9), 133-138.
30. Sadullayev, U. (2024). EDWARD ALLWORTH AND THE STUDY OF MODERN UZBEKS. Modern Science and Research, 3(2), 303-308.
31. Shokir o'g'li, S. U. (2024). MODERN SCIENCE AND RESEARCH. MODERN SCIENCE, 2181, 3906.
32. Sadullayev, U. (2024). ETHNOGENESIS AND ETHNIC HISTORY OF THE UZBEK PEOPLE. Modern Science and Research, 3(2), 355-361.
33. Shokir o'g'li, S. U. (2024). MODERN SCIENCE AND RESEARCH. MODERN SCIENCE, 2181, 3906.
34. Sadullayev, U. (2024). THE CONCEPT OF JADIDISM AND ITS ESSENCE. Modern Science and Research, 3(2), 631-636.
35. Sadullayev, U. (2024). MIRZA SIROJ HAKIM AND HIS LEGACY. Modern Science and Research, 3(2), 902–910.
36. Sadullayev, U. (2024). THE NEIGHBORHOOD IS THE CRADLE OF VALUES. Modern Science and Research, 3(1), 607–613.
37. Shokir o'g'li, S. U. (2023). The History of the Creation and Formation of the Neighborhood. American Journal of Language, Literacy and Learning in STEM Education (2993-2769), 1(10), 480-485.
38. Sadullayev Umidjon Shokir O'g'li, (2023). THE IMPORTANCE OF THE MAHALLA SYSTEM'S REFORMATIONS IN NEW UZBEKISTAN. International Journal Of History And Political Sciences, 3(10), 25–30.
39. Shokir o'gli, S. U. (2023). The Essence of State Policy on Youth in New Uzbekistan. American Journal of Language, Literacy and Learning in STEM Education (2993-2769), 1(9), 554-559.
40. Sadullayev U. (2023). THE ROLE OF THE NEIGHBORHOOD IN RAISING A SPIRITUALLY MATURE GENERATION. Modern Science and Research, 2(10), 488–493.
41. Sadullayev, U. (2023). ABOUT THE EMERGENCE OF THE CONCEPT OF NEIGHBORHOOD. Modern Science and Research, 2(12), 722–727.

42. Sadullayev Umidjon Shokir O'gli, . (2023). ELUCIDATION OF ISSUES OF THE HISTORY OF BUKHARA GUZARS IN O. A. SUKHAREVA AND HER STUDIES. *International Journal Of History And Political Sciences*, 3(11), 30–35. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ijhps/Volume03Issue11-07>
43. Sadullayev, U. (2023). O'zbekistonda xotin-qizlarga berilayotgan e'tibor: mahalla boshqaruvida xotin-qizlarning roli. In *Oriental Conferences (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 551-556)*. OOO «SupportScience».
44. Shokir o'gli, U. S. (2023). *MILLIY QADRIYATLARIMIZ ASROVCHISI*. *Journal of new century innovations*, 35(1), 79-80.
45. Sadullayev, U. (2023). THE ROLE OF THE NEIGHBORHOOD IN THE SOCIAL DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIETY. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(10), 755–757.
46. Sadullayev, U. (2023). THE ROLE OF WOMEN IN NEIGHBORHOOD MANAGEMENT IN UZBEKISTAN. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(9), 132-135.
47. Gadayeva, M., Toshpo'latova S., & Sadullayev, U. (2024). *TARIX FANLARINI O`QITISHDA MUZEYLARNING O`RNI*. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(12), 994–1003. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/58747>
48. Sadullaev, U. (2024). *EDUCATION AND ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE: A NEW ERA OF OPPORTUNITY*. *Medicine, Pedagogy and Technology: Theory and Practice*, 2(6), 238–241. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/mpttp/article/view/41188>
49. Toshpo'latova S., Gadayeva, M., & Sadullayev, U. (2024). *SHARQ ALLOMALARINING DIDAKTIK QARASHLARI*. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(12), 985–993. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/58746>